

Exploring Eco-Friendly Materials for the Partial Replacement of Cement in Concrete: A Comprehensive Review

Hardiksinh Jadeja¹, Nirav Patel²

¹*Civil Engineering, Parul University*

²*Civil Engineering, Parul University*

Abstract— This review investigates various eco-friendly materials suitable for partial cement replacement in concrete, highlighting their potential to improve mechanical properties and minimize environmental impact. The materials analyzed encompass industrial by-products such as silica fume, rice husk ash, and fly ash, alongside waste materials like coconut shell ash, eggshell powder, and ceramic powder. Their effectiveness was assessed based on key properties like compressive strength, workability, and durability. Findings suggest that each material provides distinct advantages, influenced by its composition and proportion used. For example, silica fume and metakaolin notably enhance strength and durability, whereas sawdust ash and waste paper pulp contribute to reducing the carbon footprint. This review concludes that incorporating these supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs) in concrete not only boosts sustainability but also encourages efficient resource use and waste management.

Keywords— eco-friendly materials, partial cement replacement, concrete, mechanical properties, environmental impact, industrial by-products, silica fume, rice husk ash, fly ash, coconut shell ash, eggshell powder, ceramic powder, compressive strength, workability, durability, supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs), sustainability, resource efficiency, waste management.

I. INTRODUCTION

The demand for sustainable construction materials has increased due to a growing awareness of environmental challenges and the construction industry's significant contribution to global carbon emissions. The production of Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) is responsible for approximately 8% of global CO₂ emissions. This situation has encouraged researchers to explore eco-friendly alternatives that can partially replace cement without compromising or enhancing the performance characteristics of concrete. This review investigates a variety of supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs) derived from industrial by-products, agricultural residues, and other waste materials. These alternatives, such as fly ash, silica fume, rice husk ash, metakaolin, and glass powder, have demonstrated promise in improving concrete properties like strength, workability, and durability, while also addressing sustainability concerns. By systematically analyzing the properties and performance of these materials, this paper offers a comprehensive overview of their potential applications and limitations, contributing to the advancement of greener concrete solutions.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Common Materials for Partial Replacement of Cement

Lime

The research conducted by **Hemanshu Verma** examines how partially substituting Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) with hydraulic lime affects the properties of concrete and mortar, particularly focusing on compressive strength and shear bond strength. The results indicate that incorporating lime up to 15% enhances the compressive strength of concrete cubes, but going beyond this percentage leads to a notable reduction in strength. Moreover, the bond strength of lime mortar increases with higher lime content, which is attributed to the material's capability to penetrate the pores of masonry units, creating a robust interlocking structure during the curing process. Overall, while the use of hydraulic lime appears promising for enhancing sustainability in construction, it is essential to pay careful attention to optimal replacement ratios to maintain the desired performance characteristics.{1}

The study by **Ku. Mani Kandhan and V.K. Karunakaran** investigates how partially replacing Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) with hydraulic lime affects concrete behavior. The research uses M-30 concrete mixtures, substituting cement with lime at different ratios (0%, 25%, 50%, 75%) to evaluate the compressive strength and shear bond strength of both concrete and mortar. The results indicate that the compressive strength of lime concrete cubes increases with the addition of lime up to 25%, but significantly declines beyond that point. Conversely, the shear bond strength of lime mortar improves as lime content increases, suggesting better adhesion properties. These findings highlight that while hydraulic lime can enhance certain concrete properties, it is essential to optimize the replacement percentage to achieve the desired performance results in construction applications.{2}

Nancy L. Holland, Anne B. Nichols, and John M. Nichols investigate the potential of using lime as a partial replacement for cement in concrete, particularly examining its impact on physical properties like compressive strength. Their findings reveal a linear decrease in compressive strength with increasing lime percentages, which requires adjustments in water content to ensure adequate workability. While conventional cost analyses focus mainly on initial construction costs, this study stresses the need to consider long-term environmental expenses related to Portland cement production. The results indicate that increasing water content could improve the strength of lime-rich mixes without affecting workability. Future research will explore the economic implications and the long-term durability of lime-enhanced concrete compared to traditional mixtures.{3}

Dr. A. Anbuhezian and S. Sathish Kumar explore the potential of using groundnut shell as a partial substitute for fine aggregate and lime powder as a replacement for cement in concrete. Their experimental research assesses different percentages of groundnut shell (5%, 10%, 15%, 20%) along with a consistent 20% replacement of lime powder. The results show that compressive, split tensile, and flexural strengths improve with up to 10% groundnut shell, after which there is a noticeable decline in strength. The ideal mix consists of 10% groundnut

shell and 20% lime powder, illustrating that these substitutions can enhance the mechanical properties of concrete while fostering sustainable practices through the use of waste materials.{4}

Wendimu Gudissa and Abebe Dinku investigate the effects of partially substituting Portland cement clinker with limestone powder, focusing on how this impacts the physical and chemical properties of cement paste and hardened mortar. Their research indicates that replacing up to 15% of ordinary Portland cement with finely milled limestone (4000-4500 cm²/gm) can achieve compressive strengths that are comparable to 100% ordinary Portland cement. However, replacing 25-35% leads to lower strengths that are more suitable for masonry applications. The study shows that finer limestone enhances hydration rates and promotes early strength development, positioning Portland limestone cement as a sustainable option for Ethiopia's construction industry, particularly in terms of reducing CO₂ and NO₂ emissions. The authors suggest that further research into the material's durability and cost-effectiveness is essential to optimize its application in the industry.{5}

Bilal Kamal Mohammed and Bayan Salim Al-Numan explore the potential of limestone powder (LP) as a partial replacement for cement in both normal- and high-strength concrete, focusing on the mechanical properties and punching shear behavior of flat slabs. Their research examines concrete mixtures with LP replacement ratios of 0%, 5%, 15%, and 20%. The findings show that normal-strength concrete benefits from up to 5% LP, enhancing its slump, while high-strength concrete experiences increased slump with higher LP levels. Although the compressive strength of normal-strength concrete declines with more LP, it improves in high-strength concrete with lower replacements (up to 10%). Importantly, slabs with 5% and 10% LP display higher ultimate shear loads than control specimens, indicating that LP can enhance punching strength similarly to traditional mixtures. The study concludes that substituting up to 10% of cement with LP can maintain punching load capacity, affirming its suitability as a sustainable construction material without compromising structural integrity.{6}

The research conducted by **A. Jayasri** examines the effects of partially substituting cement with lime powder and coarse aggregates with cockle shells in M30 grade concrete to tackle the growing demand for natural aggregates and address environmental issues. The results indicate that workability declines as replacement proportions increase, with slump cone test outcomes showing a drop from 50 mm (conventional) to 79 mm (15% lime and 30% cockle shells). However, compressive strength saw a notable improvement, reaching a peak of 38.5 N/mm² for replacements of 5% lime and 10% cockle shells, while tensile strength reached 2.94 N/mm². The study concludes that incorporating 5% lime powder and 10% cockle shells not only boosts concrete strength—demonstrating increases of 16.94% in compressive strength and 14.39% in tensile strength compared to traditional concrete—but also fosters environmental sustainability through the reuse of waste materials.{7}

A study by **A. Jayaraman** explores the impacts of substituting natural sand with M-sand and replacing ordinary Portland cement with limestone powder on the engineering characteristics of concrete, including compressive strength, tensile strength, and water absorption. The research addresses the growing demand and depletion of river sand, demonstrating that both M-sand and limestone powder can serve as effective alternatives. The findings indicate that a water/cement ratio of 0.50 yields optimal results, particularly for M25 grade concrete, with compressive strengths ranging from 18.14 to 36.72 N/mm², tensile strengths from 10.76 to 18.5 N/mm², and flexural strengths from 12.21 to 40.08 N/mm². The study concludes that the combination of M-sand and limestone powder can create concrete suitable for structural uses, while also underscoring the necessity for further research on additional structural properties.{8}

Anusha and Ramya's study investigates the mechanical properties of M40 concrete by incorporating limestone powder and copper slag as partial substitutes for cement and fine aggregate, respectively. The researchers replaced cement with varying percentages of limestone powder (10%, 15%, and 20%) and adjusted the fine aggregate content with copper slag at levels of 0%, 20%, 40%, 60%, 80%, and 100%. Their findings reveal that the compressive strength peaked at 65.19 N/mm² after 28 days when using 60% copper slag and 15% limestone powder, which represents an increase of 25.05% compared to conventional concrete. Additionally, flexural and split tensile strengths also reached their maximum at 80% copper slag with 15% limestone powder, showing increases of 33.73% and 6.9%, respectively. However, strengths began to decline when the proportions exceeded these optimal levels. The study concludes that the ideal mix of 60% copper slag and 15% limestone powder not only improves mechanical properties significantly but also mitigates environmental impact and reduces production costs.{9}

Fly Ash

Jagdish Virupakshi Patil's study examines the effects of incorporating fly ash as a partial substitute for cement in concrete mix designs. The research emphasizes that fly ash, which is a by-product of coal combustion, can enhance concrete properties like workability, compressive strength, and resistance to various environmental challenges. It categorizes fly ash into Class F and Class C based on its chemical makeup. The paper highlights several advantages of using fly ash, such as reduced water requirements, decreased heat of hydration, and improved long-term durability. Additionally, a mix design targeting a concrete strength of 50 N/mm², featuring a 30% fly ash replacement by weight of the total cementitious material, is presented. The findings indicate that fly ash concrete demands less cement and water compared to standard concrete, resulting in both economic and environmental benefits.{10}

The research by **K.V. Sabarish** investigates the effects of partially substituting cement with fly ash in M25 and M40 concrete mixes, focusing on its influence on strength and cost. The study examines fly ash replacement levels of 0%, 10%, 20%, 30%, and 40%, evaluating compressive strength at 7, 14, and 28 days, as well as split tensile strength at 56 days. Findings indicate that increasing fly ash content results in a reduction of both compressive and split tensile strengths. Nonetheless, incorporating fly ash significantly decreases the overall costs of concrete production, presenting it as a viable option for minimizing environmental impact and managing industry disposal costs. However, due to the observed reductions in strength, cautious implementation is recommended.{11}

Rishabh Joshi's research examines how partially replacing cement with fly ash affects the compressive strength of M20 grade concrete. Fly ash, a byproduct of coal combustion, is recognized as a sustainable alternative that can help lessen the environmental impact associated with cement production. The study evaluates cement replacement with fly ash at levels of 0%, 10%, 20%, and 30%, measuring compressive strength at 7 and 28 days. Findings reveal that while fly ash enhances workability and durability, the compressive strength declines as the fly ash content increases. Specifically, at 30% replacement, the 28-day compressive strength is 16.35 N/mm², reflecting a 21% reduction compared to conventional concrete. The study concludes that a fly ash replacement of up to 30% is optimal, striking a balance between environmental advantages and strength characteristics.{12}

The research conducted by **Tiwary, Gagandeep and Thakur** investigates the impact of partially replacing cement with fly ash (FA) and lime in M30 grade concrete. Different concrete samples were prepared, incorporating varying proportions of fly ash and lime: 0% (control sample S0), 5% FA + 5% lime (S1), 10% FA + 15% lime (S2), and 15% FA + 10% lime (S3). The samples underwent testing for compressive strength, split tensile strength, and flexural strength at 7, 14, and 28 days. The results revealed that S2 (10% FA + 15% lime)

achieved the highest compressive strength after 28 days compared to the control mix, while split tensile strength slightly decreased across all replacement scenarios. Flexural strength improved in S1 (5% FA + 5% lime), surpassing the control mix; however, a reduction in flexural strength was noted with increasing fly ash content. The study concludes that optimal strength characteristics are attained with a balanced blend of fly ash and lime, but further increases in fly ash proportions may negatively affect performance. {13}

In their study **Padavala** investigate the impact of partially replacing cement with fly ash and substituting coarse aggregates with palm kernel shells (PKS) in lightweight concrete. The research utilized M30 grade concrete, where cement was replaced by fly ash in increments ranging from 5% to 30%. Strength tests indicated that a 25% fly ash content was optimal. Additionally, with the fly ash content fixed at 25%, coarse aggregates were replaced with PKS at 5%, 10%, and 15% ratios. The results demonstrated that the highest compressive strength was achieved with a 10% PKS replacement. The incorporation of hybrid fibers (steel and polypropylene) further improved tensile strength. Ultimately, the optimal mix—comprising 25% fly ash, 10% PKS, and 1.2% hybrid fibers—resulted in lightweight concrete exhibiting superior strength properties compared to conventional mixes, positioning it as a cost-effective and environmentally sustainable solution for construction. {14}

Bharathi investigate the potential of using seashells as a partial substitute for coarse aggregate and fly ash for cement in concrete, addressing concerns related to resource depletion and environmental sustainability. Their research indicates that seashells, primarily composed of calcium carbonate, can effectively replace traditional aggregates, thereby reducing the dependence on natural resources. Experimental findings reveal that the optimal percentage of seashell replacement for achieving maximum compressive strength is 7%, yielding a strength of 31.95 MPa, which surpasses the conventional concrete strength of 23.14 MPa. Additionally, tensile strength reaches its highest at a 5% seashell replacement (3.966 MPa), although an increase in seashell content leads to a decrease in flexural strength. Workability is also found to diminish with higher seashell percentages due to their rough texture. In conclusion, the study demonstrates that utilizing seashells and fly ash not only improves the mechanical properties of concrete but also provides a cost-effective and environmentally friendly alternative for construction, especially in coastal regions where seashell waste is abundant. {15}

Red Mud With Hydrated Lime

Ashok and Sureshkumar examine the potential of red mud, a byproduct from the Bayer process used in alumina production, as a partial substitute for cement in concrete. Their research highlights the economic and environmental advantages of using red mud, which is rich in iron, aluminum, and titanium oxides, along with other components like calcium and soda. The study conducted experiments with five levels of red mud replacement (0%, 5%, 10%, 15%, and 20%) and included 5% hydrated lime to enhance the pozzolanic activity of the mixture. The findings reveal that a 15% replacement level is optimal, resulting in a 21.71% increase in 28-day compressive strength compared to traditional concrete, alongside a 7.48% reduction in costs. Additionally, red mud was shown to enhance cement quality by reducing setting time and improving compressive strength without negatively impacting other cement properties. The study concludes that neutralized red mud (NRM) can effectively serve as a cement substitute up to 15%, offering promising applications in building materials, road construction, and the ceramic industry. {16}

Limestone and silica powder

Zareei (2017) investigated the impact of partially replacing cement with limestone powder (LP), micro-silica (MS), pumice, and lightweight expanded clay aggregate (leca) in lightweight aggregate concrete. The study examined ten mixtures with LP content ranging from 0% to 20%, while maintaining a constant 10% MS content, to evaluate properties such as compressive strength, tensile strength, water absorption, acid resistance, and impact resistance at 7 and 28 days. The results indicated that LP initially reduced short-term strength; however, a combination of 5% LP with 5% MS yielded the best mechanical and durability properties. Concrete made with leca showed enhanced durability at replacement levels of 20%, whereas pumice concrete experienced a 21% reduction in compressive strength, while leca concrete's strength increased by 4%. The addition of LP also led to lower water absorption rates (1.5-2.5%) and reduced chloride ion penetration, thereby improving durability. However, exposure to high temperatures (above 200°C) significantly diminished strength, resulting in a 50% loss compared to ambient conditions. The study concluded that the combination of LP and MS in lightweight concrete not only offers environmental advantages but also delivers satisfactory performance, making it a promising choice for sustainable construction.{17}

Barites and Lime Powder

Meenakshi (2017) examined the impact of partially replacing cement with barites and lime powder in M30 grade concrete. The study involved cement replacement levels of 0%, 10%, 20%, and 30%, with compressive strength tested at 7, 14, and 28 days. The results indicated that the mixes exhibited higher compressive strength at 7 days compared to the control, achieving up to 29.6 N/mm². However, there was no significant improvement observed at 14 days. By 28 days, the compressive strength decreased considerably across all mixes, with the highest replacement level yielding only 17.68 N/mm², compared to 36.44 N/mm² for the control. The study concluded that while barites and lime can enhance early strength, their combined use is not advisable due to insufficient long-term strength development.{18}

Phosphogypsum And Flyash

Saikhede and Satone investigated the potential of using phosphogypsum (PG) and fly ash (FA) as partial replacements for cement in M25 grade concrete. The study focused on the effects on compressive, tensile, and flexural strength by varying PG content (0%, 5%, 10%, and 15%) while maintaining FA content at a constant 20%. Additionally, a mix with 5% PG and 25% FA was tested. The results indicated that the optimal mix was achieved with 10% PG and 20% FA, resulting in a compressive strength of 33.27 MPa, a tensile strength of 3.217 MPa, and a flexural strength of 4.12 MPa at 28 days. Higher replacement levels led to a reduction in strength, attributed to excess gypsum content adversely affecting hydration. The study concluded that a combined replacement of up to 30% of cement with PG and FA can yield concrete with satisfactory strength, providing a sustainable method for utilizing these industrial by-products and decreasing cement consumption.{19}

Silica Fume

In this study, **Sachin U** investigates the impact of partially replacing cement with silica fume and coarse aggregate with river pebbles on the strength and workability of M-30 grade concrete. Silica fume was incorporated in varying proportions of 5%, 10%, and 15%, while river pebbles replaced coarse aggregates at levels of 20%, 30%, and 40%. Tests, including slump and compressive strength assessments, were conducted to evaluate the concrete's performance. The results indicated that increasing the percentage of river pebbles improved workability but led to a decrease in compressive strength, attributed to inadequate bonding between the

aggregate and cement paste. In contrast, the optimal compressive strength was observed with a 10% replacement of cement by silica fume, which enhanced strength due to the formation of additional calcium-silicate-hydrate (C-S-H) gel. The study concluded that a combination of 20% coarse aggregate replacement with river pebbles and 10% cement replacement with silica fume provided the best compromise between workability and strength. {20}

The paper by **Roy and Sil** examines the influence of silica fume (SF) as a partial cement replacement in M20 grade concrete, focusing on its effects on the mechanical properties of both fresh and hardened concrete. The findings demonstrate that the incorporation of SF enhances the cohesiveness of the fresh mix, leading to reduced segregation and bleeding. In hardened concrete, the use of SF results in increased compressive strength, split tensile strength, and flexural strength, with maximum enhancements observed at a 10% replacement level. This substitution leads to a 19.6% increase in cube compressive strength and a 16.82% increase in cylindrical compressive strength, along with improvements of 38.58% in split tensile strength and 21.13% in flexural strength. The study further indicates that M20 grade concrete with 10% SF replacement exhibits properties comparable to M25 grade concrete, facilitating a 4% reduction in construction costs. The authors conclude that SF concrete is advantageous for high-strength applications and can also effectively improve low to medium strength concretes, enhancing durability and performance, which is particularly beneficial for projects in aggressive environments and requiring rapid construction. {21}

rock dust

The study by **Dobiszewska** explores the use of rock dust as a partial cement replacement in concrete and mortar production, emphasizing its effects on mechanical properties and sustainability. This review highlights that rock dust, a by-product of geological rock grinding processes, primarily enhances cement composites through mechanisms such as the filler effect, heterogeneous nucleation, and cement dilution. The findings indicate that substituting cement with up to 10-15% rock powder does not significantly compromise mechanical properties; in fact, it can improve workability, reduce bleeding, and enhance durability by refining pore structures. The authors note that the fineness of rock dust is critical, with finer particles yielding better performance outcomes. However, higher replacement levels can lead to decreased strength and durability. Additionally, the paper discusses the potential of rock dust to mitigate environmental impacts, lower carbon emissions, and reduce reliance on natural resources, positioning it as a promising alternative for sustainable concrete production. The authors recommend comprehensive research to further investigate rock dust's pozzolanic activity, its effects on cement hydration, and long-term durability under aggressive conditions. {22}

Egg Shell Powder

The research conducted by **V. Aravind and V. Ranjith** investigates the potential of using eggshell powder (ESP) and steel slag as partial replacements for cement and coarse aggregate in concrete. The experimental findings reveal that substituting cement with ESP results in a 20% reduction in compressive strength and a decrease in tensile strength, suggesting that ESP is best utilized in conjunction with reinforcement, such as steel rods. Conversely, flexural strength improves with the addition of up to 10% ESP. The study also highlights the increased carbonation potential of the mixture, which may influence long-term permeability. When steel slag is used as a replacement for coarse aggregates, the results demonstrate strength improvements with up to 40% substitution, attributed to the slag's shape and surface texture; however, exceeding this percentage leads to increased porosity and a subsequent decrease in strength. The optimal replacement levels identified are 40% for steel slag and 25% for manufactured sand (M-sand), achieving a compressive strength of 48.7 MPa. The combination of 25% M-sand and 40% steel slag is deemed optimal for applications not subjected to marine

conditions. Overall, this research positions ESP and steel slag as effective alternatives for cement and coarse aggregate, offering significant environmental benefits through reduced consumption of natural materials and effective waste management. {23}

Brick powder

The research conducted by **Rehan Arif** examines the potential of Waste Brick Powder (WBP) as a partial replacement for cement in concrete, utilizing replacement levels of 5% and 10%. A series of tests were performed, including assessments of slump, density, compressive strength, flexural strength, splitting tensile strength, Schmidt Hammer, Ultrasonic Pulse Velocity, and microscopic analysis. The findings indicated an enhancement in workability attributed to the smooth surfaces and rounded edges of WBP particles. Although a minor decrease in density was noted due to the lower density of WBP relative to cement, the inclusion of WBP significantly improved compressive, tensile, and flexural strengths. This enhancement was linked to the formation of additional Calcium Silicate Hydrate (CSH) and the filling of voids by pozzolanic products. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) analysis verified the development of stable ettringite and an increase in CSH content, while Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) highlighted elevated levels of calcium and silicon, suggesting improved material quality. Ultimately, the study concluded that replacing 10% of cement with WBP resulted in a 10% rise in compressive strength, a 24% increase in tensile strength, and a 12% boost in flexural strength after 28 days of curing. {24}

Meta kaolin

The investigation by **Narmatha** delves into the use of metakaolin as a supplementary cementitious material aimed at enhancing the performance of high-performance concrete (HPC). The study assessed the impact of substituting ordinary Portland cement (OPC) with metakaolin at various levels—specifically 5%, 10%, 15%, and 20%—by weight. Key mechanical properties, including compressive, split tensile, and flexural strengths, were the focal points of the research. Results indicated that the mix incorporating 15% metakaolin achieved the most significant improvements, showcasing a compressive strength of 72.7 MPa at 28 days, which corresponds to a 17.45% increase compared to the control specimens. The findings suggest that utilizing metakaolin at this optimal replacement level not only enhances the strength properties of HPC but also contributes to improved durability, positioning it as a promising alternative for sustainable construction practices. {25}

The research conducted by **CH Jyothi Nikhila and J D Chaitanya Kumar** (2015) investigates the impact of using Metakaolin (MK) as a partial cement replacement in high-strength concrete (M70 grade). Metakaolin, obtained from the calcination of kaolin clay, was incorporated at various replacement levels—specifically 0%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25%, and 30%—to evaluate its influence on compressive, flexural, and tensile strengths, as well as its durability when exposed to acidic environments and elevated temperatures. The findings revealed that a 15% replacement of MK resulted in the highest compressive strength and enhanced resistance to both hydrochloric acid (HCl) and sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄), along with improved thermal stability up to 100°C. However, beyond the 15% replacement level, there was a slight decline in strength. In conclusion, the incorporation of Metakaolin significantly enhances the performance of high-strength concrete, establishing it as a valuable supplementary {26}

Glasspowder

The study conducted by **Dr. G. Vijayakumar, Ms. H. Vishaliny, and Dr. D. Govindarajulu** evaluated the potential of glass powder as a partial substitute for cement in concrete, aiming to reduce the environmental footprint of cement manufacturing. Cement was replaced with glass powder at varying levels—10%, 20%, 30%, and 40%—and the resulting concrete was tested for compressive, tensile, and flexural strengths over a 60-day period. The results demonstrated that finely ground glass powder (less than 75 μ m) significantly increased compressive strength by up to 33.7%, tensile strength by 4.4%, and flexural strength by 100% compared to conventional concrete. Moreover, the study emphasized that using glass powder mitigates the risk of the alkali-silica reaction (ASR), which can compromise concrete stability. The optimal replacement level was identified as 30%, offering substantial strength improvements without causing long-term detrimental effects, thereby establishing glass powder as a viable and sustainable alternative to cement in concrete production. {27}

Nayem kazi (2017) investigated the potential of using waste glass powder as a supplementary cementitious material (SCM) in concrete production. The research included both clear and colored glass, which were analyzed chemically through X-ray fluorescence (XRF) to ensure compliance with ASTM C618 standards for pozzolanic materials. The analysis confirmed the suitability of both glass types for concrete. Concrete and mortar specimens were prepared with cement replaced by glass powder at levels ranging from 0-25%. It was observed that incorporating glass powder slightly increased the flow of mortar and had only a minor influence on workability. Compressive strength tests indicated that concrete containing glass powder showed improved strength compared to the control samples, especially at longer curing periods. The highest strength was achieved at 20% replacement, demonstrating that ground glass can effectively contribute to pozzolanic activity. Moreover, the use of admixtures led to a notable improvement in compressive strength at early curing stages. The study concluded that replacing up to 20% of cement with waste glass powder can enhance the mechanical properties of concrete while promoting sustainability by reducing cement consumption and utilizing waste materials effectively. {28}

Marble dust powder

Ranjan Kumar and Shyam Kishor Kumar examined the feasibility of utilizing Marble Dust Powder (MDP) as a partial cement replacement to mitigate environmental concerns linked to industrial waste. The MDP, which is a by-product from marble quarrying and rich in calcium oxide, was evaluated for its influence on the strength characteristics of concrete. The study incorporated five concrete mixes with MDP replacement levels of 0%, 5%, 10%, 15%, and 20%, while maintaining a consistent water-cement ratio of 0.43. The experimental results indicated that compressive strength increased by 8.05% at 10% MDP substitution, while the maximum split tensile and flexural strengths were achieved at 15% MDP replacement. Beyond 15%, an increase in MDP content resulted in a reduction of strength. The study concluded that MDP could serve as an effective partial cement substitute, contributing to sustainable construction by utilizing waste materials while enhancing the mechanical properties. {29}

Sawdust

Marthong conducted an experimental investigation to evaluate Sawdust Ash (SDA) as a partial substitute for Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC), aiming to assess its suitability for sustainable construction applications. The study included OPC grades 33, 43, and 53, with SDA replacing cement at levels of 0%, 10%, 20%, 30%, and 40%. The experimental findings indicated that the compressive strength of concrete increased with higher OPC grades, but early strength development only reached 50-60% of the target values at 28 days, suggesting that SDA

initially exhibited a retarding effect on strength gain. Water absorption showed a reduction of up to 20% SDA substitution; however, durability under sulfate exposure remained unchanged, indicating that SDA's effectiveness diminishes beyond a 10% replacement threshold for all OPC grades. The study concluded that SDA could be utilized to improve sustainability in concrete production without compromising performance, though its application is best limited to a 10% replacement level.{30}

Ceramic powder

Le Li (2024) investigated the feasibility of utilizing waste ceramic powder (CWP) as a partial cement replacement in concrete to mitigate environmental impacts, considering the high carbon emissions from cement manufacturing (around 8% of global CO₂ emissions) and the enormous quantities of ceramic waste generated annually (over 22 billion tons). The experimental study evaluated concrete properties with varying CWP replacement levels up to 20%. Results indicated that concrete with CWP replacement maintained acceptable compressive strength and water absorption characteristics, while also showing improvements in thermal conductivity. Moreover, the CWP-infused concrete did not experience significant mechanical damage after exposure to fire for 30 minutes. The study recommends limiting CWP replacement to 20% to preserve the mechanical properties and emphasizes the need for additional research to optimize workability and further investigate the material's thermal and fire performance. The findings highlight CWP as a sustainable alternative for cement replacement, offering the benefits of reduced waste and enhanced concrete properties.{31}

Raval investigated the potential of ceramic waste powder as a sustainable substitute for ordinary Portland cement (OPC) in M20 grade concrete, aiming to address the disposal issues of ceramic waste while promoting environmentally friendly construction practices. The study replaced OPC with ceramic waste powder at 0%, 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, and 50% levels and measured the compressive strength of concrete at 7, 14, and 28 days. Findings revealed that compressive strength reached its maximum at 30% replacement, achieving a strength of 22.98 N/mm². Beyond this level, further replacement led to a reduction in strength. Economically, using 30% ceramic waste powder in concrete resulted in a 12.67% cost savings, making it a viable, eco-friendly alternative for sustainable construction. The study highlights that 30% replacement is optimal for achieving both strength and cost-efficiency, encouraging the recycling and utilization of ceramic waste in concrete production.{32}

Waste paper pulp

Ahmad investigated the feasibility of using waste paper sludge ash as a partial replacement for cement in M25 grade concrete to promote sustainability and reduce the environmental footprint of cement production, which is a major source of greenhouse gas emissions. The study involved replacing cement with sludge ash at 5%, 10%, 15%, and 20% levels, assessing the resulting concrete's compressive strength, tensile strength, water absorption, and dry density after 28 days of curing. Results indicated that a 5% replacement level provided the highest compressive strength, which was 15% higher than that of conventional concrete. However, further increases in sludge ash content led to decreased strength and reduced workability due to greater water absorption. Notably, concrete mixes with 20% sludge ash exhibited a 4.58% reduction in density, making the concrete significantly lighter. The study concluded that waste paper sludge ash can serve as a cost-effective and eco-friendly cement substitute, addressing waste disposal concerns and promoting resource conservation in concrete manufacturing when used at optimal replacement levels.{33}

Balwaik and Raut explored the potential of using waste paper pulp as a partial substitute for cement in concrete, evaluating replacement levels from 5% to 20% by weight in both M-20 and M-30 concrete mixes. The study aimed to offer a sustainable alternative to the landfill disposal of paper sludge. Findings revealed that the

compressive, splitting tensile, and flexural strengths improved with the addition of waste paper pulp, peaking at 10% replacement. However, further increases in pulp content resulted in decreased strength. Additionally, workability in fresh concrete was adversely affected by higher pulp content due to its water-absorption properties. The research identified the optimal mix proportion as being within the 5% to 10% replacement range, effectively balancing hydration needs and mechanical performance. Ultimately, the study concluded that integrating waste paper pulp into concrete could lead to cost savings for the paper industry while fostering eco-friendly construction practices.{34}

Sugarcane Bagasse Ash

Abdulkadir, Oyeyobi, and Lawal examined the use of sugarcane bagasse ash (SCBA) as a partial replacement for cement in concrete, emphasizing its pozzolanic properties. Concrete cubes were prepared with SCBA replacement levels of 0%, 10%, 20%, and 30%, and their compressive strengths were evaluated at various curing ages. The SCBA, obtained by burning sugarcane bagasse at 700°C, contained a total silica, alumina, and ferric composition of 80.55%, meeting ASTM-595 standards. Results showed a decrease in compressive strength with increasing SCBA content: control specimens reached 26.8 N/mm² at 28 days, while specimens with 10%, 20%, and 30% replacements achieved compressive strengths of 22.3 N/mm², 20.1 N/mm², and 17.3 N/mm², respectively. The pozzolanic activity index was satisfactory for the 10% (83.2%) and 20% (75%) replacements, indicating its potential for use in reinforced concrete. The study concluded that SCBA can effectively reduce the environmental impact and costs associated with concrete production, recommending a maximum of 20% replacement for improved sustainability.{35}

Mangi explored the use of sugarcane bagasse ash (SCBA) as a partial cement replacement in concrete, specifically examining M15 and M20 grades. The research involved substituting cement with SCBA at levels of 0%, 5%, and 10% by weight. Findings revealed that incorporating SCBA resulted in an average compressive strength increase of 12% at the 5% replacement level for M20 grade concrete after 28 days. Additionally, SCBA enhanced workability, eliminating the need for super-plasticizers. This study underscores SCBA's potential as a sustainable alternative to traditional cement, contributing to waste reduction and improved concrete performance. The authors recommend further investigations to assess additional properties of concrete affected by SCBA.{36}

Coconut Shell Ash

The study by **Nagarajan** examines the potential of coconut shell ash (CSA) as a partial substitute for ordinary Portland cement (OPC) in concrete, aiming to address environmental issues and the rising costs of cement. The authors emphasize that OPC production significantly contributes to CO₂ emissions, prompting the search for alternative materials to reduce waste and enhance sustainability. CSA was produced by combusting coconut shells and then sieving to achieve the required fineness. Various concrete mixes were formulated with different levels of OPC replacement using CSA, and compressive strength tests were conducted at various curing ages. The results indicated that while CSA can lower cement usage and CO₂ emissions, higher replacement percentages resulted in reduced compressive strength. The optimal performance was observed at a 10% replacement level, achieving a compressive strength of 31.78 N/mm² after 28 days. These findings underscore CSA's potential for sustainable concrete production, highlighting the need for a careful balance to maintain desired material properties.{37}

Rice husk ash

The study conducted by **Kaarthik Krishna** explores the feasibility of utilizing rice husk ash (RHA) as a partial substitute for ordinary Portland cement (OPC) in concrete to encourage sustainable construction practices. Given that OPC production accounts for over 5% of global CO₂ emissions, the authors underscore the importance of alternative materials such as RHA, which contains a high reactive silica content of 90%-95%. The research involved a mix design based on the Indian Standard method, analyzing four levels of RHA replacement (5%, 10%, 15%, and 20%). Findings revealed that RHA incorporation significantly influenced both fresh and hardened concrete properties. Workability decreased with increased RHA due to its high surface area, which absorbed water and led to lower slump values. Compressive strength reached its peak at a 10% replacement level (29.3 MPa after 28 days), while higher percentages resulted in a decline in strength. Similar trends were observed for split tensile and flexural strengths, which performed optimally at 10% RHA but diminished at higher levels. The study concludes that RHA can effectively replace cement up to 10%, providing environmental benefits without compromising concrete quality. {38}

Obilade (2014) investigates the characteristics of Rice Husk Ash (RHA) as a partial substitute for Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) in concrete, utilizing replacement levels of 0%, 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, and 25%. The findings indicate that the compacting factor diminished with an increase in RHA content, highlighting a reduction in workability attributed to the higher silica levels, which required more water for proper mixing. Compressive strength tests demonstrated that while the strength of control samples improved over time, the strength of samples containing RHA declined with higher replacement percentages. Notably, the optimal RHA replacement level was identified to be between 0-20%. This research underscores the potential of RHA as an accessible pozzolan, suggesting further investigations into its effects on structural applications and durability assessments. {39}

III. CONCLUSION

The review reveals that the partial replacement of cement with eco-friendly materials offers significant benefits in terms of sustainability and performance enhancement. Each supplementary cementitious material (SCM) has distinct characteristics that influence concrete's mechanical and durability properties. Materials like silica fume and metakaolin demonstrate considerable improvements in compressive and tensile strength, making them ideal for high-strength applications. Agricultural wastes such as rice husk ash and sugarcane bagasse ash contribute to waste reduction and environmental sustainability, though their usage may necessitate adjustments in concrete mix design to optimize performance. Overall, the integration of these SCMs in concrete production not only reduces the carbon footprint but also promotes the recycling of industrial and agricultural by-products, supporting sustainable construction practices. Future research should focus on long-term performance assessments and the development of optimized mix designs for diverse construction scenarios.

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